

S3E START

RESEARCH TEAMS PORTFOLIO

**INTRODUCING THE SELECTED DEEP TECH
PROJECTS FROM SOUTHERN EUROPE**

Funded by
the European Union

LIST OF RESEARCH TEAMS

- [BIOSCREEN](#) Oxidative Stress Determination
- [BLOOD2POWER](#) Powering Smart Health with Your Blood
- [BREASTSCREENING-AI](#) Let machines do machine stuff, let doctors do human stuff.
- [C-ANAL](#) AnusVision: Clear sight, safe procedure
- [CPSE](#) Comprehensive Pathogen Surveillance Ecosystem
- [DOPANTS](#) Antimicrobial and Biodegradable Plastics
- [ECOPLAN](#) AI-powered Platform for Sustainable Construction

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LIST OF RESEARCH TEAMS

- [GENESIS](#) Safe plug and play off-grid production system
- [MIRALS](#) ASO BLOCKER for miR-129
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- [ONCOMAGNETOSWEEP](#) Magnetical Sweep of Tumor Cells
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- [UPWIND](#) Harnessing the Sky, Powering the Future

OXIDATIVE STRESS DETERMINATION

The BioScreen project presents a technology for plant health monitoring tailored into a small portable device based on electrochemical measurements for oxidative stress. The device can be attached to plants to monitor plant health (influenced by drastic environmental conditions), giving rise to BioScreenPlant. Our BioScreenPlant solution addresses and solves the lack of modern equipment for real-time monitoring of field crop health encountered worldwide in precision and smart agriculture. Farmers will benefit from a portable, user-friendly device for rapid decision-making in field crop farming operations.

INSTITUTION

ICECHIM - NATIONAL INSTITUTE FOR RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT IN CHEMISTRY AND PETROCHEMISTRY

COUNTRY

ROMANIA

SECTOR

AGRICULTURE

 IOANA HOSU

Scientific Researcher

 LUMINITA DIMITRIU

Scientific Researcher

POWERING SMART HEALTH WITH YOUR BLOOD

Blood2Power technology is a pioneering power-generating system that harnesses electrical energy from the movement of body fluids (e.g., blood) to power medical devices. Empowered by the patient's own blood, this project focuses on the development of an intelligent vascular graft, the iGraft. This self-powered smart vascular graft will autonomously sense and monitor its performance, transmitting data and alerts to healthcare systems through telemetric capabilities, thereby preventing device failure.

INSTITUTION

i3S - INSTITUTE FOR RESEARCH AND INNOVATION IN HEALTH

COUNTRY

PORTUGAL

SECTOR

HEALTH

 INÊS GONÇALVES

Principal Investigator

 ANDREIA PEREIRA

PostDoc Researcher

 DANIELA SOUSA

Project Manager

 HERBERT MIDDLETON

Research Fellow

 SALOMÉ LUÍS

Research Fellow

BreastScreening-AI

LET MACHINES DO MACHINE STUFF, LET DOCTORS DO HUMAN STUFF.

BreastScreening-AI develops advanced AI-driven diagnostic tools integrating mammography, ultrasound, and MRI data to enhance breast cancer detection accuracy. Our technology aids radiologists by reducing diagnostic times and minimizing false positives and negatives, thereby improving patient care and workflow efficiency in clinical settings.

INSTITUTIONS

INSTITUTO SUPERIOR TÉCNICO
AND UNIVERSITY OF COIMBRA

COUNTRY

PORTUGAL

SECTOR

HEALTH

FRANCISCO MARIA CALISTO

Researcher

CARLOS SANTIAGO

Researcher

ANDRÉ FADIGA

Researcher

ANUSVISION: CLEAR SIGHT, SAFE PROCEDURE

The patented anoscope is a device applicable to endoscopes enabling full visualization of the anus while ensuring gas tightness during diagnostic exams. It prevents endoscope rotation, reducing the risk of rectal injuries. Applicable to all colonoscopies for diagnostic and therapeutic purposes, such as hemorrhoid treatment.

INSTITUTIONS

UNIVERSITY OF PADOVA
AND UNISMART - FONDAZIONE
UNIVERSITÀ DI PADOVA

COUNTRY

ITALY

SECTOR

HEALTH

 LINO POLESE
Principal Investigator

 FRANCESCA RIZZI
TTO

 ILARIA TONIOLO
Researcher

CPSE

COMPREHENSIVE PATHOGEN SURVEILLANCE ECOSYSTEM

PathoTrack and AgriSafe by Comprehensive Pathogen Surveillance Ecosystem (CPSE) leverage AI to enhance pathogen surveillance through next-generation sequencing analysis. Designed for public health and agriculture, our systems identify pathogens, assess outbreak risks, and integrate seamlessly into local and global frameworks, especially aiding LMICs with limited expertise.

INSTITUTION

ANKARA UNIVERSITY

COUNTRY

TURKEY

SECTOR

HEALTH & AGRICULTURE

 GÜLTEKİN ÜNAL

Bioinformatics Specialist

 CIHAN İSPANOĞLU

Senior Systems Architect

 EGE DEDEOĞLU

Consultant - Scientific Writer

 HAMZA YUSUF ALTUN

QCM Diagnostics

ANTIMICROBIAL AND BIODEGRADABLE PLASTICS

DOPANTS

DOPANTS innovates with polymer nanocomposites currently aiming to enhance safety and sustainability in medical consumables such as catheters, ventilators, surgical handles, and more. We plan to produce filaments and masterbatches that combat infections, offer customization via 3D printing and molding, and ensure durability. Our technology provides superior passive benefits over competitors, complementing existing sterilization techniques while reducing environmental impact.

INSTITUTION

HELLENIC MEDITERRANEAN UNIVERSITY

COUNTRY

GREECE

SECTOR

HEALTH

M. STYLIANAKIS

Chemist PhD

V. TZATZADAKIS

Mech.Engineer PhD

A. MASTROGIORGI

Nursing Student

E. PERIVOLA

Nursing Student

M. FRAGKIOGLOU

Nursing Student

EcoPlan

EcoPlan

AI PLATFORM FOR SUSTAINABLE CONSTRUCTION

EcoPlan revolutionizes material selection in the AEC industry through AI-powered recommendations and a comprehensive database. With 80% accuracy in sustainability assessment and real-time cost estimates, it streamlines project planning, reduces errors, and ensures compliance with evolving sustainability regulations. EcoPlan simplifies the complex process of material selection, saving time, costs, and enhancing sustainability for architects, engineers, construction firms, and stakeholders, marking a significant step towards greener, more efficient building practices.

INSTITUTION

VILNIUS UNIVERSITY

COUNTRY

LITHUANIA

SECTOR

CONSTRUCTION

 MARIUS KRIUKOVAS

Researcher & Software Developer

 GRETA CERSKUTE

Researcher & Architect

GENESIS

SAFE PLUG AND PLAY OFF-GRID PRODUCTION SYSTEM

The recreational and fishing maritime sectors need to decarbonize but are still too dependent on diesel/petrol engines. Alternatively, hydrogen is the vector with the highest energetic potential, but it's only considered green when produced through large-scale water electrolysis, associated to renewable grid electricity and stored in high-pressure tanks or in liquid at very low temperatures, which is not ideal for off-grid. GENESIS is the solution! It is a safe plug-and-play off-grid production system that assures clean, pure hydrogen and borate with high value.

INSTITUTIONS

FEUP - FACULTY OF ENGINEERING AT U. OF PORTO
& INEGI - INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION
IN MECHANICAL AND INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING

COUNTRY

PORTUGAL

SECTOR

MARITIME

 ALEXANDRA PINTO
Researcher

 DIOGO SILVA
Researcher

 HELDER NUNES
Researcher

 LUCAS MARCON
Researcher

MIRALS

ASO BLOCKER FOR MIR-129

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) is a fatal, incurable neurodegenerative disorder with adult onset. The disease is characterized by a degeneration of motor neurons and death within 3-5 years from the diagnosis. Currently, there is no approved treatment able to significantly reverse damage to motor neurons or change clinical course of the disease. We have identified a significant altered expression of microRNA-129 (miR-129) in ALS. This miR plays a key role in neuronal processes and likely in other cell types. We showed that administration of a patented inhibitor of miR-129 in a mouse model of ALS can extend life survival and improve motor functions and predict efficacy for different ALS forms.

INSTITUTION FOUNDATION IRCCS CA' GRANDA
OSPEDALE MAGGIORE POLICLINICO

COUNTRY ITALY

SECTOR HEALTH

STEFANIA CORTI
Researcher

LINDA OTTOBONI
Researcher

MAFALDA RIZZUTI
Researcher

MARGHERITA CHIERICI
TTO

ALESSANDRO CERVI
TTO

FROM PLANTS TO PLANTS

Plant-parasitic nematodes (PPN) are a major threat to global agriculture causing substantial economic losses for the affected crops. Plants infected with PPN show general stunt aerial/root growth resulting in low biomass production, affecting its yield and productivity. Bio-based and sustainable solutions to combat PPN are crucial in agriculture. Derived from the Portuguese endemic flora, NemAway is a fast and efficient action bionematicide applied to a broad spectrum of PPN. NemAway is environmentally-friendly and can be easily delivered for the crops by contact or soil fumigation.

INSTITUTION

UNIVERSITY OF ÉVORA

COUNTRY

PORTUGAL

SECTOR

AGRICULTURE

 CLÁUDIA VICENTE
Researcher

 MARGARIDA ESPADA
Researcher

PEDRO BARBOSA
Researcher

 MADALENA MENDONÇA SILVA
Researcher

MAGNETICAL SWEEP OF TUMOR CELLS

Metastatic cancer accounts for over 90% of cancer-related deaths. By targeting the circulating tumor cells (CTCs), the key players in cancer progression, OncoMagnetoSweep is a magnetic extracorporeal device able to remove CTCs from whole blood. Capturing 60% of CTCs in a single passage, our product improves the metastatic cancer treatment, by decreasing the side effects and the treatment time & number of sessions, with a global cost reduction. For high-risk cancer patients, OncoMagnetoSweep prevent early metastasis formation, significantly enhancing prognosis and survival rates.

INSTITUTIONS

I3S - INSTITUTE FOR RESEARCH & INNOVATION IN HEALTH AND CBQF - CENTRE FOR BIOTECHNOLOGY & FINE CHEMISTRY

COUNTRY

PORTUGAL

SECTOR

HEALTH

 MARTA LARANJEIRA
Group Leader, Researcher

 DIANA FONSECA
Researcher

 LUISA FIALHO
Researcher

 NATACHA ROSA
TTO

ONCOMETS

IN VITRO MONITORING TOOL FOR BREAST CANCER

Our project introduces an in vitro diagnostic tool for breast cancer (BC) monitoring, driven by a groundbreaking circulating biomarker discovery platform. With enhanced BC biomarker identification capacity and accuracy, ONCOSECRET, our proprietary circulating biomarker panel, promises to revolutionize BC monitoring. Unlike invasive tumor biopsy and radiation-based methods, ONCOSECRET will provide accurate, non-invasive, real-time monitoring, enabling early detection and reducing mortality rates. Easily integrated into healthcare systems, ONCOSECRET will empower oncologists to combat BC effectively.

INSTITUTION

i3S - INSTITUTE FOR RESEARCH AND INNOVATION IN HEALTH

COUNTRY

PORTUGAL

SECTOR

HEALTH

ANA RIBEIRO
Researcher

JOANA PAREDES
Researcher

RITA CARVALHO
Researcher

INÊS CONDE
Researcher

BRUNO FREITAS
Researcher

BÁRBARA MACEDO
Researcher

YOUR T CELLS. YOUR IMMUNITY.

Absence or reduction in Immune system's T cells can severely compromise your body defenses against several insults like cancer and infections. Although our body can produce new T cells, this capacity is lost with age or damage to the organ responsible for this process, the thymus. THYMI offers for the first time the possibility to produce in laboratory patient-specific T cells that can be ready for use to supplement patient immunity with no risk of transplanted cell rejection or side-effects.

INSTITUTION

i3S - INSTITUTE FOR RESEARCH AND INNOVATION IN HEALTH

COUNTRY

PORTUGAL

SECTOR

HEALTH

RUTE PINTO

Researcher

PEDRO FERREIRINHA

Researcher

HARNESSING THE SKY, POWERING THE FUTURE!

To tackle climate change and provide the necessary energetic transition and electricity access to locations that are currently deprived of such an essential resource or supplied by pollutant and fuel hungry diesel generators, the UPWIND team proposes ZEPHYRUS, a generator based on Airborne Wind Energy (AWE). This device consists of a tethered kite that converts energy using a generator placed on the ground. Our product offers a portable, affordable, easily deployable, clean energy conversion system that is a fitting solution for remote communities and economic activities.

INSTITUTION
FEUP - FACULTY OF ENGINEERING
AT UNIVERSITY OF PORTO

COUNTRY
PORTUGAL

SECTOR
ENERGY

 FERNANDO FONTES
Researcher

 LUÍS TIAGO PAIVA
Researcher

 MANUEL FERNANDES
Researcher

 SÉRGIO VINHA
Researcher

 GABRIEL FERNANDES
Researcher

 RUI DA COSTA
Researcher

18 JUNE 2024

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